

1 **Type 1 gamma delta T cells (Tyd) and type 17 Tyd can be distinguished based on expression of an**
2 **NK cell activation marker, NKG7.**

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8 Blood cells of the adaptive immune system can be identified as B or T lymphocytes. T lymphocytes are
9 characterized based on expression of the T-cell receptor as either alpha beta T cells or gamma delta T
10 cells. While alpha beta T cells engage in conventional antigen-specific responses by engaging
11 MHC:peptide complexes expressed on antigen presenting cells, gamma delta T cell defense is less well
12 understood but features recognition of non-classical ligands like lipid antigen expressed by CD1d and
13 interactions with MHC family receptors MR1 and MICA/MICB. Tyd cells are defined based on the nature
14 of their cytokine production as either type 1 or type 17 Tyd. We measured total transcription with next
15 generation sequencing to define the essential differences in Tyd1 and Tyd17. Tyd17 and Tyd1 were
16 defined by difference in expression of the natural killer cell activation marker, NKG7. We recently
17 demonstrated that NKG7 is functional in immunologic contexts involving loss of tolerogenic capacity, like in
18 stem cell transplant patients with graft versus host disease, and in solid organ transplant patients
19 experiencing acute rejection of the donor tissue. A second function we described for cells expressing
20 NKG7 was participating in tumor surveillance through engagement with killer cell surface receptor
21 KIR2DL3 and specific interactions of KIR2DL3 with class I MHC receptor HLA-V which marked cells
22 undergoing or having undergone transformation, which was further characterized by TCR receptor
23 switching from abTCR to ydTCR, indicating Tyd cells participated in tumor surveillance together with
24 natural killer cells. Together we concluded that a subset of Tyd cells can express the natural killer cell
25 activation marker NKG7, that the Tyd cells lineages Tyd1 and Tyd17 are defined by difference in
26 expression of NKG7, and that Tyd cell recruitment in tumor surveillance and homeostatic functions
27 requiring enforcement of tolerogenic signals at barriers and in transplant settings that feature natural killer
28 cell activation use a specific Tyd subset, Type I NKG7+ Tyd cells (Tyd1).